

TEACHING STUDENTS TO THE STAGES OF CLOTHING SKETCHING

Atayeva Farangiz Allaberganovna

Bukhara Institute of Engineering Technology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7550705>

Abstract. *This article talks about the stages of drawing sketches of clothes, the dimensions of the human body, the position of clothes on the body, the color of clothes, how to draw clothes on the body. Information about design, designer, fashion designer, artist is mentioned.*

Keywords: *sketch, designer, artist, drawing, silhouette, decor.*

INTRODUCTION

The expansion of the export potential of our country has given new tasks to every field of production. In particular, the development of the sewing industry, providing our people with high-quality, beautiful clothes is one of the important tasks facing light industry workers, especially designers. In order to fulfill these tasks, it is necessary to produce sewing products, increase their size, improve their quality, create new designs of clothes, and create enterprises with new highly efficient equipment.

Currently, sewing enterprises of our country are filled with equipment produced on the basis of the latest scientific and technical achievements. Complex mechanization and automation of technological processes by equipping machines and equipment with various devices continues, but our designers also have a great responsibility.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

In the course of this scientific article, I reflected the stages of drawing clothes on the human body for designers in the above-mentioned tailoring. This shows the initial drawing process. The positive results of my scientific research aimed at developing quality products and increasing work productivity will be reflected.

Production of sewing products is one of the important tasks facing the light industry. In this regard, the development of new types of materials and their new designs, methods of processing them, first of all, ensuring the high quality of the manufactured products, paying attention to the balance of colors, taking into account the satisfaction of the needs of the population of all ages I think that the assortment of clothes should be constantly improved and updated.

Hundreds of new goods and new forms are released to the consumer market every day and every year to meet the demands of our contemporaries, whose industry has developed and their tastes are growing. The creators of these items and forms are definitely designers. The field of modern design is very delicate, in terms of scale, it is much wider than other fields, it is a special “universe”.

Today's designers need not only to draw well, but also to acquire the necessary knowledge of the basics of engineering, innovation, robotics, sociology, psychology and physiology, management and marketing; it is also necessary to be knowledgeable about the history of culture and our national values, to keep up-to-date with new materials and constructions, advanced technologies, and design news of developed countries.

In our opinion, in order to train quality personnel in creative design in our republic, the following should be implemented:

1. Encouraging children to design, architecture, innovation and creativity by organizing construction games, special lessons, activities, and clubs from a young age;
2. Increasing the hours of classes aimed at increasing painting and creativity in the educational system (taking into account that children understand faster through visual means than words) through informational means;
3. Creating an opportunity for students to be in regular contact with production (in addition to the main current practices, organizing talented students to work as apprentices in a company or private workshops at least 2 days a week after classes), great effect continuing the age-old "teacher-disciple" tradition.

Design (eng. design-project, drawing, painting) is a term that represents the types of design activities aimed at forming the aesthetic and functional qualities of the environment of objects.

Designer - the designer is engaged in the development of drawings, changes the model features of the product according to the sketch of the artist-modeler or the customer.

A **fashion designer**-technologist chooses or develops the actual methods of sewing a product, searches for the most suitable processing methods that simplify the process of making a new item.

The artist - fashion designer is engaged in creating sketches - he looks for new shapes and silhouettes of the product on paper, develops possible finishing options, draws the product design in detail.

It is known that a fashion designer is a specialist in sewing clothes, designers of these clothes, as well as creators of experimental samples. The tasks of the designer profession include: determining the image and style of the client (buyer), discovering new technological and design solutions, developing decor, choosing colors and materials, thinking about accessories and other additions. Because a fashion designer thinks in every way and then creates a sketch.

Steps for drawing clothing sketches on the human body:

How to draw a sketch? Everything is suitable for this - pencil, felt-tip pen, colored pencil, paint, etc. First of all, use a regular pencil, which will allow you to make changes to your drawings. Also, when you draw with lines, your sketch will come out faster and with accurate

Figure 1. Diagram of the division of the human body.

measurements. Your goal is not to draw an academically correct model, but it is to create a new sketch of a certain outfit for you. The first step is to divide the paper in half, and then divide it into 9 by a straight line drawn through the middle (Figure 1).

No modern outfit is complete without a designer sketch. Model pictures are the embodiment of couture ideas that define new trends in fashion.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Not every designer can create a work immediately. In order to realize the idea, it is necessary to study it in depth.

Figure 2. The scheme of dividing the human body into 9

work requires more careful drawing.

Carefully drawing the main lines, we check the symmetry of the picture. In this case, it is advisable to make the hairstyle universal, because it may be needed in the future if you want to draw something else (Figure 3). But you should not refuse to draw faces, we will focus on clothes. Now we need a black pen. Gently define the image of the girl. Remove all extra lines. Carefully copy the sketch to paper with a soft pencil so as not to spoil the work.

Figure 4. The stage of drawing and painting the sketch model.

Mark the vertical axis on the paper that the silhouette will "hold". For convenience, divide this arrow into equal parts whose height corresponds to the size of the head: 8-9 parts for a man, 7-8 for a woman, 5-6 parts for a child (Figure 2).

By marking the central axis with light lines, you can start sketching the front view.

At our next stage, we will draw the head, outline the arms, legs, shoulders, chest line, waist and hips. We mark the knee and wrist joints with a circle.

In the next step, we will add volume to our sketch. This

Figure 3. Step of drawing the face of the model.

The next step is to sketch the outfit. Here you will need to know the latest trends in the fashion industry. And if you still haven't decided on an image, browse fashion magazines for inspiration. Apply contours with light strokes.

Our sketch is almost ready. So here is the finished sketch of the model. All the main work is done. Now we can draw and paint all the design elements - pockets, seams, decorations, decor, etc. (Figure 4).

CONCLUSION

I think sketching a model using the drawing steps outlined in this article will help students at least a little.

REFERENCES

1. Allaberganovna, A. F. . (2022). Improvement of the Design of Working Bodies of Modern Presses to Increase Shape-Saving Characteristics During Moisture-Heat Treatment of Clothes. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 28, 17–19. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/549>
2. Allaberganovna, A. F. (2022). Improvement of the Design of Working Bodies of Modern Presses to Increase Shape-Saving Characteristics During Moisture-Heat Treatment of Clothes. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 28, 17-19.
3. Allaberganovna, A. F. (2022). Improvement of the Design of Working Bodies of Modern Presses to Increase Shape-Saving Characteristics During Moisture-Heat Treatment of Clothes. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 28, 17-19.
4. Allaberganovna, A. F. (2022). KIYIMLARGA NAMLAB-ISITIB ISHLOV BERISHDA SHAKLNI SAQLASH XUSUSIYATINI YAXSHILASH MAQSADIDA ZAMONAVIY PRESSLARNING ISHCHI ORGANLARI KONSTRUKSIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(2), 117-122.
5. F. Atayeva (2022). KIYIMLARGA NAMLAB-ISITIB ISHLOV BERISHDA SHAKLNI SAQLASH XUSUSIYATINI YAXSHILASH MAQSADIDA ZAMONAVIY PRESSLARNING ISHCHI ORGANLARI KONSTRUKSIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. *Science and innovation*, 1 (A5), 221-225. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7050207
6. Allaberganovna, A. F. (2022). KIYIMLARGA NAMLAB-ISITIB ISHLOV BERISHDA SHAKLNI SAQLASH XUSUSIYATINI YAXSHILASH MAQSADIDA ZAMONAVIY PRESSLARNING ISHCHI ORGANLARI KONSTRUKSIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(2), 117-122
7. Абдумавлонова Ф. Х., Сейтов А. Ж. СХЕМЫ ГОРНЕРА НА МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКОМ ПАКЕТЕ MathCAD //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. CSPI conference 3. – С. 811-816.

8. Сейтов А. Ж., Абдумавлонова Ф. Х. Решение геометрических задач с помощью математического пакета MAPLE //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 933-941.
9. Abdumavlonova F. THE CONCEPT OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL SPACE AND CONSTRUCTION OF VOLUMETRIC BODIES ON THE MATHEMATICAL PACKAGE GEOGEBRA //Science and Innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 8. – С. 938-950.
10. Salaeva, M. N., Nodirova, Z. Y., Sidiqov, R. R., & Abdumavlonova, F. X. (2021). PISA TADQIQOTIDA KREATIV FIKRLASHNI BAHOLASH MAQSADI VA ASOSIY E'TIBORI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(5), 1358-1364.
11. Сейтов А. Ж., Абдумавлонова Ф. Х. ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКОГО ПАКЕТА МАТНСАД ДЛЯ ПРОВЕДЕНИЯ УРОКА НА ТЕМУ «ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛЬНЫЕ МОДЕЛИ» В 11-КЛАССЕ //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 8. – С. 153-160.